

Comparative Default Risks with Automobile Lease Financing Through Conventional and Islamic Banks

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Abstract

In this study, it is investigated that how Conventional or Islamic lease has lower default risk in market. Primary data, it was collected from Khyber's Banks and both quantitative and qualitative techniques were used for the analyses of occurrence of default risk. Conventional Lease found to be more likely to default than Islamic Lease. The reason for this is inflexibility, hard terms, uncertain instalment amounts, and sole discretionary power of bank to change interest rate without asking the customers. Specifically, age and income tend to reduce the risk of default while price and interest rate increase the risk of being defaulted. Moreover, automobile type and unemployment show a higher risk of default. The paper not only contribute to the existing literature but also could be helpful to improve the bank's leasing products, reducing default risk and contribute to the bottom line of the banks.

Key Words: *Islamic Lease, Conventional Lease, Default Risk, Ijara Wa-Iqtina, Islamic Finance, Ijara*

1. INTRODUCTION

Automobile industry of Pakistan contributes around PakRs. 50 billion (@ 3 % of GDP) to national exchequer. The industry employs around 1.8 million people whilst producing 1.8 million motorcycle and 200,000 vehicles with an investment of Rs. 92 billion (Propakistan, 2015). According to Siddiqui (2008), automobiles are usually financed by two ways: paying the price of automobile straight away to the vendor by the purchaser (direct purchase); and by taking a loan to purchase automobile and then repay the amount with interest back (lease contracts). A lease is a mutual contract between two parties (i.e. customer & bank) in which the bank leases (rents) commonly used real assets. Like as car, motorcycle, equipment, machinery, computer etc., sold at fixed interest rates for a specific period to the customers with an option to purchase at the end of a mutual agreement (Ibrahim, 2000; Brian, 2000a; Siddiqui, 2008). This specific proper business is called conventional lease, whereas Islamic lease (Ijara) refers to transferring the use of an object (its usufruct) for a specific time-span to the lessee and ownership of object which remains with the lesser itself. In other words, Ijara is a sale of usufruct not of a physical entity (Ibrahim, 2000; Brian, 2000a).

There is large number of customers especially working class who just cannot find it easy to buy a car straight away due to shortage of funds rather need to finance it through banks and other leasing organizations. Similarly, banks have to extend financing facilities to customers to contribute to the bottom line of the business on one hand but on the other it has to be very cautious in advancing loans for the higher risk of default involved in it. Therefore, there is a need to find out which facility is less risky and more attractive to larger customers and why. Therefore, our research aims to investigate whether conventional or Islamic automobile lease financing has lower default risk. We collect our primary data in the form of questionnaires and interviews from customers, employees, and managers of the bank and find out that conventional lease has higher default risk for its rigid, inflexible, and hard terms and conditions as compared to Islamic Lease financing. The next section briefly introduces the case, Bank of Khyber, followed by comparative review of literature on conventional and Islamic lease financing.

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE BANK OF KHYBER

The provincial legislative assembly of Khyber Pakhunkhwa, Pakistan is established in 1991. It has declared by administration as a scheduled bank in 1994 by the State Bank of Pakistan. It has the privilege of being one of the three government banks in the country with total 34 branches in which 16 are Islamic and 18 offer services in conventional banking. It has fifteen board-of-directors, one chairperson, three key executives, and twenty-seven departmental in charge. Its products and services consists of advances, deposit, ATM, online banking, consumer finance, microfinance, agri-credit, and service charges (The bank of Khyber,

2009). Its customers include people from all lifestyles including individuals seeking loan for personal/commercial use, sole proprietors, partnership businesses, companies and Government.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section explores conventional lease, Islamic lease, basic principles of Islamic finance, similarities and differences between conventional and Islamic lease (ijara wa iqtina), default risk, collateral, automobile and lease characteristics, and some theoretical frameworks.

2.1 CONVENTIONAL LEASE

In conventional financing, there are two main types of lease. One financial lease, where “*the service provider expects to cover full cost (or almost the full cost) of object, addition of interest in actual cost for the specific time period of lease*” (Arnold, 2008) and second operating lease, which “*commits a short-term contract to the lessee, which can be ended at short notice. It may not be certainly expected to last for the entire asset's life and so the finance house has the responsibility to search an alternative use for freed asset*” (Arnold, 2008).

Arnold (2008) reports that after the expiry of the operating lease contract agreement an asset might be further leased out. This implies that the finance provider is exposed to risk of getting the asset further leased or selling it in the market. In both cases it requires expertise and cost resources. The other issue is that the lesser bears the loss in case the leased asset rapidly obsolesces and the cost associated with maintenance and insurance. However, according to Arnold (2008), the advantages of lease include small initial outlay and availability of finance when other finance sources are not available. Similarly, it gives tax relief and a fixed-rate of financing. Moreover, it transfers the risk of obsolescence to the finance provider.

According to El-Din and Abdullah (2007), a conventional lease can base on different principles. Lease is perceived as an ordinary type of loan and thus forms a creditor and debtor relationship between the lesser and the lessee (BOK, 2010b). Lease contract is initiated, upon requirements are fulfilled by customer, irrespective of whether the customer gets the product or not at the time of signing the contract (The Bank of Khyber, 2009; Meezan Bank, 2009). Customer signs a standard agreement which incorporates details of the transaction, conditions and warranties, parties' rights and obligations, offenses, and penalty as specified by the Hire-Purchase Act 1967 (El-Din and Abdullah; 2007).

Leased asset's price is calculated by adding the prevailing interest rate to the purchase price. The interest rate is floating based on the annual rate. The periodic payments (instalments) are calculated by dividing the purchase price by period of agreement which usually ranges from 3 to 8 years (El-Din and Abdullah, 2007). The bank leases the asset without giving much consideration to the purpose and origin of a transaction, that is, whether the transaction is Islamic or un-Islamic such as gambling, alcohol, and prostitution¹ (Usmani, n.d. Nov 11, 2009; The Bank of Khyber, 2009).

Conventional lease is governed under the Hire- Purchase Act 1967. Under the facility bank offers assets for lease as specified in the First Schedule of the Act, which comprises of consumer goods and automobiles. The facility is offered to individuals, sole proprietors, partnerships, and corporate companies (BOK, 2010b). Term charges, period of financing, and early settlement are dealt the same way as in Islamic lease. Term charges are calculated according to the prevailing market rate by the formula set in the Hire-Purchase Act. Period of financing ranges 12 months to 84 months. Regarding early settlements the rules specified in the Hire-Purchase Act are observed. However, it is bank's right whether to grant a rebate to its customer or not (El-Din and Abdullah, 2007; BOK, 2010b).

In conventional lease the bank bears no responsibility for fully damaged commodity, that is, bank is not responsible for any repair provided the lessee has no fault in the damage. The bank is only interested in the principal and interest amounts that the lessee has to pay to the bank In other words, only the lessee is accountable for the maintenance of the leased asset and responsible for insurance of the asset (Ibrahim, 2000; The Bank of Khyber, 2009; BOK, 2010b).

In general speaking, a conventional bank is exposed to interest rate and default risk of the borrower (Fatemi and Fooladi, 2006). Nevertheless, it is partially covered by collateral taken before advancement of loan. To avoid big losses on loans in case of default, conventional banks legally acquire first right on the assets of the individual/company. The bank holds the title of ownership as a security for the hire-purchase loan (Horn and Wachowicz, 2005).

¹ Alcohol, Gambling and Prostitution may be legal somewhere but un-islamic everywhere.

It has been a common practice to pay a deposit before leasing the asset out. The purpose of deposit is to secure the company against future loss, negligence, misuse or misconduct caused by the hirer. The deposit payment differs from place to place and from company to company. For instance, in Iran the amount of deposit is a minimum of 20% of the price of the asset and is considered as a part of the rent duration of the lease (El-Din and Abdullah, 2007; BOK, 2010b). Sattar et al (2002) and El-Din and Abdullah (2007) cited that a deposit payment is considered as a security deposit. Customer will pay the required amount as deposit to bank which ranges 20% to 50% of the leased asset. Both conventional and Islamic lease require a deposit payment from its customers.

The lease contract becomes void when the terms and conditions are not fulfilled as per the contract, for instance, an act of default in due payments. When one party breaches the terms and conditions, it results in a loss to the other party that needs to be compensated. In conventional lease, if the lessee defaults in paying the instalments on time are subject to late payment penalty charges which go to the bank's profit (Usmani, 2002, Meezan Bank, 2004, cited in El-Din and Abdullah (2007). Late penalty charges are recovered from defaulter at the rate of around 8.0 % per annum (Usmani, 2009).

Last but not the least, lesser must subscribe a comprehensive insurance policy for the leased asset (State Bank of Pakistan, 2010; BOK, 2010b). Moreover, lesser does not assume any responsibility for any costs of the asset and all the responsibility of maintenance is transferred to the lessee (State Bank of Pakistan, 2010)

2.2 BASIC PRINCIPLES DEVELOPED BY ISLAMIC FINANCE

The basic principles of any Islamic finance are based on prohibiting Riba (interest), Gharar (uncertainty), legal purpose and origin of financing, and risk sharing.

2.2.1 Riba (Interest)

To prohibit Riba, that is, giving and taking interest is prohibited in Islamic finance.

2.2.2 Gharar (Uncertainty)

To ban Gharar and to make sure everything in the transaction is feasible, certain, clear, transparent and understandable to both the parties.

2.2.3 Purpose and Origin of financing:

Never allow the trading and financing business of illegitimate (against Islamic law), which are ethically and socially non-beneficial assets for the commodities. Such activities like as gambling den, finance a casino and trading of pork and liquor etc., (Mervyn and Latifa, 2001; Iqbal, 2001; Usmani, n.d. Nov 11, 2009; & Gait and Worthington, 2008).

2.2.4 Risk Sharing

The Islamic finance lays emphasis predominantly on risks-sharing for pre-offered profits and losses. Removal of debt-based financing or desirability for economic cash based transaction or other such activities or contracts where parties are not exploited in the contracts (Ibrahim, 2000 ; Gait and Worthington, 2008; & BOK, 2010b).

2.3 ISLAMIC LEASE

Like conventional lease, Islamic lease can be broadly divided into types, that is, operating lease and Ijara Wa Iqtina. The former one does not end up into ownership whereas the later ends up into ownership. Operating lease is a contract wherein possession of a particular intended usufruct of the leased asset is exchanged for a consideration (Guddah,). We confine our research to the later one as it is mostly commonly used mode of financing in the area. Ijara Wa-iqtina, an innovative form of Ijara, is a combination of a lease contract and sale contract in one trading document but both the contracts work separately and in sequence, that is, the sale contract becomes active after the expiry of lease contract². However, the lessee has the option to enter into the second contract to purchase the leased asset from the owner at an agreed price. The price of the asset will be determined as per the market conditions and a necessary profit to the bank. It is noteworthy that the price of the asset cannot be predetermined because it breaches principles of Sharia (Islamic Law). Similarly, it has no conditional obligation on lessee because a pre-conditioned contract is prohibited by Sharia (El-Din and Abdullah, 2007). However, at the end of the contract, the bank offers the customer to buy the product against the security payment that the customer has already made to the bank at the time of initiating the lease contract (Ibrahim ,2000; Siddiqui, 2008; & Usmani, n.d. Nov 11, 2009).

2.3.1 MECHANISM OF IJARA WA-IQTINA

²In this study Islamic lease or Ijara or Ijara Wa-iqtina are used interchangeably

According to El-Din and Abdullah (2007), Ijara Wa-iqtinain involves three main parties, that is, customer (buyer), bank (financing company), and vendor. The mechanism is as follow:

- a. *A bank buys a vehicle (an asset) from a dealer as per the customer order.*
- b. *Bank sold vehicle to customer for agreed rental payments and for specific time-period.*
- c. *Customer will agree to accept responsibility for its road tax, insurance and other maintenance costs.*
- d. *After completion of time period, sale and purchase agreement will be signed by bank as customer.*

Islamic lease is a mode of financing which is based on profit and loss sharing. More precisely, the sale and purchase agreement is executed between both parties the bank (seller) and customer (buyer). According to Bughuddah (2001) and El-Din and Abdullah (2007), Islamic purchase consists in two contracts like as ijara (lease) it is a beginning of contract and second is completion of ownership to lessee by seller or may be it call based contract (Usman n.d, Nov 11, 2009; Bughuddah, 2001 and Elahi, 2000, cited in El-Din and Abdullah, 2007; BOK, 2010b).

2.4 DEFAULT RISK

According to Hussein et al., (2007), the serious banking problems are occurring due to lax credits for borrowers and counterparties mean default risk factors. Poor portfolio risk management, poor contemplation to ever-changing economic conditions and other external factors (legal risk, withdrawal risk, risk) are associated with development and innovation of products among others (Carey, 2001; Fatemi and Fooladi, 2006; Freeman et al, 2006; Hussein et al, 2007; Siddiqui, 2008; Ludwig, 2009). According to Anthony and Linda (2002), structural increase in bankruptcies, disintermediation, more competitive margins, declining and volatile values of collateral, the growth of off-balance-sheet derivatives, technology and the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) risk-based capital requirements are the key reasons that boost the significance of understanding and effective employment of credit risk (default risk). Brian (2000b; P. 2) defines default risk as “the possibility that loss could arise from non-payment or late payment of a financial obligation by a customer”. In the research a person is considered default when he/she does not or pays late an instalment.

2.5 COLLATERAL

According to Jimenez et al. (2006), before advancing funds, banks or financial institutions usually take into account collateral, interest rate, maturity, size and possible covenants. “Collateral is the functional characteristics of borrower like as lender (specialization), nature of borrower-lender (duration), credit market (competition), size of loan, and macroeconomic conditions like as business cycle” (Jimenez et al., 2006). Moreover, there are some important aspects of the collateral that the bank consider before advancing money to the customer, that is, the specific type of collateral pledged by the borrower, the current value of the collateral, and the bank’s activities in the time when a customer suffers financial distress (Elsas and Krahen, 2000). Moreover, the quantity and quality of collateral required from a customer depends upon borrower-lender relationship (relationship lending), the level of competition in the credit market, and net costs and benefits associated with the lending (Jimenez et al., 2006). It can be defined as amount of collateral increases with decrease in loan size and increases in interest (Manove and Padilla, 2001 and 1999); Jimenez et al. 2006).

According to Bester (1985, 1994), cited in Elsas and Krahen (2000), there are differing views on the expected default risk and the provision of collateral. However, the study they conducted found that there is no serious relationship between the degree of collateralization and its expected default risk rather it is mainly aimed at controlling the strategic position of lender in relation to the borrower and other lenders in the future lending renegotiations. However symmetry in bank and borrower is not smooth then collateral demands for riskier borrowers (Boot et al. 1991; Jimenez and Saurina, 2004). Similarly, Jimenez et al. (2006) found that low-quality borrowers are required higher collateral than high-quality borrowers. He further adds that borrowers will offer more collateral and benefit from low interest rate on the loans if the quality of credit refers to his/her private information. Likewise, research conducted by Jimenez and Saurina (2004) reveals that if asymmetry is high (for instance, if adverse selection is significant) than collateral can sort out borrowers by insuring the credit quality.

2.6 FACTORS FOR CONSIDERATION

As the number of factors for consideration are countless, therefore, some of the significant factors are contemplated such as character, capital, capacity, collateral, cycle (or economic) conditions which is referred

to Expert System or “five Cs of credit” (Anthony and Linda, 2002; Stell, 2009). According to Stell, (2009) who suggests another significant factor of ‘change’ to ‘five Cs of credit’ due to ever-changing world to better measure the credit risk. He suggests that change should be taken into account not only at the time of underwriting a loan rather it should be throughout the loan life. Consistency and subjectivity are the two limitations of the ‘expert system or five Cs of credit’. Consistency refers to the criteria of factors that are supposed to be considered for a variety of borrowers while subjectivity suggests the weights (relative importance of variable) given to each factor (Anthony and Linda, 2002).

The probability of default and prepayment depends upon loan characteristics i.e. age of vehicle, loan amount, loan-to-value (LTV), monthly payments, contract rate and (Agarwal et al, 2008). Likewise, increase in loan-to-value ratio (LTV) raises the probability of default and lowers the probability of prepayment. Normally, a lender is not interested in the make and model of a car rather is more interested in the borrower’s credit worthiness (credit score) and the down payment (Agarwal et al., 2008). Further, they found some interesting patterns between the make, model, new and old car, for instance, a loan on a new car has a higher probability of prepayment, whereas on an old car it has higher probability of default (Agarwal et al., 2008).

Similarly, an increase in income also increases the probability of prepayment, whereas a rise in unemployment increases the probability of default. Further, luxury cars have high probability for prepayment, whereas economy cars have higher probability of default (Agarwal et al, 2008).

2.7 THEORITICAL FRAMEWORKS

To enhance the performance of a bank, they need to search out the associated risks in the running business. Target can be achieved by classifying the default risks like as proprietary risks and vendor-market risks (Fatemi and Fooladi, 2006). A proper addressing the matter and applying different appropriate models could be helpful for assessing, measuring and controlling credit risk internally. Meanwhile, the vendor-market risk models are best dealing for the external credit risks (Algorithmics, CreditMetrics+, Loan Pricing Corporation, KMV’s Portfolio Manager, and McKinsey’s Credit Portfolio View” (Fatemi and Fooladi, 2006). For instance, analysis of samples and applications of different tests could be helpful in assessing the probability of occurrence of possible events in future and their outcomes (Nason, 2009).

The importance of credit risk models is to identify the counterparty’s default risk (Hussein et al., 2007). Whereas such risks refers to the debt-holder who does not receive interest on principle due (Default Risk, 2006). According to Stell (2009), a large number tools and techniques have applied for the identification of default risk on the loans (quantitative and qualitative analysis). The quantitative analysis technique mainly focused on numbers that are based on financial statements that is assumed that firm will keep functional in in future, while Horn and Wachowicz (2005) declared such case remain often uncertain in past as well as may be in future. The qualitative analysis technique is focused on ‘expert system or five C’s of credit’ on repaid loans. For the prevention of any unpleasant circumstances, lender should use qualitative and quantitative analytical tools for the better judgment. The dynamic nature of risk could change the factor in the borrower and external circumstances (Nason, 2009; Stell. 2009).

Mostly, the internal models are playing a significant role in better evaluation of risks associated loans. The deciding person like as branch manager to grant a loan might be his personal judgement or expertise about the person playing major role in developing or minimizing the risk factor (Anthony and Linda, 2002).

Neural network (Witkowska, 2006), is an internal risk model that compute and evaluates the past loan proposals, which are based on the knowledge fed by best human experts (Schneider, 2001). This system is based on personal inputs, weights, or may be hidden units. The cited neural expert system may not show the audience a transparent evaluation process. There are the chances of relatively important variable and internal structure of the network that leads to lack of accountability. It could be steps in evaluation process while cannot be checked. However, neural network system could be useful for classification of loans, bonds or the prediction of defaults or recoveries (Wu and Wang, 2000; Anthony and Linda, 2002). The Credit Scoring Systems (CSS) is being most commonly used model, which is based on key factors involved in the identification of probability of default obtain quantitative scores (Avery et al., 2009). It can be helpful in identification of probability of default as well as the classification of loans or bonds.

Summarizing the literature review, different factors such as automobile characteristics, lease characteristics, collateral, bank requirements and borrower characteristics play an important role in the success or failure of lease contract. Religious and easy terms of the contract motivates customers to opt one of the two financing

facility. Factors such as automobile age, loan amount, loan-to-value (LTV), monthly payments, contract rate, time of origination (year and month) and payoff year, and borrower's characteristics such as credit score, monthly disposable income, and borrower age, and also the unemployment rate etc are the prominent determinant of default risk.

Retaining adequate collateral, and identifying, understanding, assessing, measuring and controlling the associated risks with the business can be achieved by classifying risks. There can be different types of risk such as proprietary risks and vendor-market risks (Fatemi and Fooladi, 2006). Following classifying the risk, it then needs to be addressed by applying appropriate models. Models of risk includes proprietary risk models for assessing, measuring and controlling credit risk internally and vendor-market risk models for dealing with external credit risk effectively such as "Algorithmics, CreditMetrics+, KMV's Portfolio Manager, Loan Pricing Corporation, and McKinsey's Credit Portfolio View" (Fatemi and Fooladi, 2006).

Knowing about these will help improve the banking and other leasing companies to overhaul their products and offer the products with higher demand and less default risk in the market. Concluding the literature review, there is a need to investigate the comparative higher default risk associated with the both conventional and Islamic lease.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this section we brief about sample data, sources of data, and tools for data analysis and finally variables that used to come up with some conclusion. In sections 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 we describe sample study, sources of data and tools for analysis respectively. Finally section 3.4 defines variables used in the analysis.

3.1 SAMPLE STUDY

The Bank of Khyber is the sample study under investigation. Only Primary data in the form of questionnaires are collected from customers, employees and managers from two local branches of the bank in the same locality.

3.2 SOURCES OF DATA

The main sources for data collection are questionnaires, several banks web sites, central bank publications, journals, books, newspapers and other publications.

3.3 TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

Microsoft Excel is used for analysis of the questionnaires. Simple averages are calculated and explained in the analysis in the percentage form.

3.4 VARIABLES

Demographic factors, lease features, automobiles characteristics, and bank requirements/consideration are employed as variables to find out the comparative default risk.

4. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

In the chapter both quantitative (questionnaires) and qualitative data (open ended questionnaire and interviews) are analysed respectively. Customer questionnaire consists of four sections namely borrower's characteristics, Loan (lease) features, automobile characteristics, and bank considerations (requirements) whereas employee questionnaire contains the same sections and questions but are asked from a banker's point of view.

4.1 QUESTIONNAIRE ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Total 40 questionnaires were sent out to two types of respondents, that is, employees (bankers) and customers (those who have financed their automobiles through conventional or Islamic lease). Responses collected from employees and customers were 17 and 26 respectively. Interestingly, in total 26 customers 21 and 5 customers financed their automobiles through Islamic lease and conventional lease respectively.

4.1.1 DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS

The findings revealed that significantly high number of males (81%) financed their automobile through lease than females (19%) in which 19% and 81% were conventional and Islamic lease respectively, which attribute to income, education, cultural and religious values of the people. Interestingly, males were more likely to default than females. Religion and risk sharing found to be most significant reasons for selecting Islamic lease.

Increase in age and income negatively related to default risk. The significant age group, which is less likely to default, is 'over 35 years' whereas 'Under 25 years' age group the most likely to default. Similarly, significant income group with least probability of default is 'Over Rs. 50,000' whereas the most likely to default income group is 'Under Rs. 30,000'.

The significant employment status group is 'private employee' where more than half of customers lie. Reasons for the 'private employee' being a significant employment status group may be due to the reasons that the income of private employees is usually higher than the government employees in Pakistan. Interestingly, 'unemployed' group has been opined by bankers to be more risky in terms of customers' default followed by 'Self Employed' group. However, the risk of default in unemployed group is more than three times higher for conventional lease than Islamic lease. Similarly, the most significant groups with more likely defaults are 'No Education' and 'Matriculation or Lower' with 35% each of total automobile leasing. As per the bankers the 'New Borrower' is more likely to default whereas the 'Old Borrower' is more than four times lower in default than for the 'New Borrower'. It may be due to the reasons that the bank does not know much about the new customers and thus sometimes fails to judge correctly. Bankers view about the likely default of customers is that secondary customers are more than three times likely to default than primary customers.

4.1.2 LEASE FEATURES

The most significant relationship between likely default and automobile price groups are 'More than Rs. 15,00,000' with 46% and 'Rs. 600,000 to 10,00,000'. The weakest relationship between likely default and automobile group can be found in 'Less than Rs. 600,000' group which may be due to the low price and greater probability of return in time.

The number of customers increase with increases in number of instalments which implies that banks and customers are more interested in large number of instalments as it is easy for customers to pay instalments in time and the bank earns profits/interest on their investment. The most popular category for conventional lease is '36 to 48' with 8% followed by 'More than 48' and '18 to 36' instalment categories with 8% each whereas for Islamic lease it is 'More than 48' category with 53% which is more than three times greater than its related '36 to 48' instalment category.

4.1.3 AUTOMOBILE CHARACTERISTICS

The dominant reasons for choosing an automobile are 'High Functionality' with 43% and 'Durability' with 33% followed by 'Others' with 19%. Interestingly, conventional leases were taken with 0% in 'Availability', 'Status Symbol' and 'Others' and 8% and 12% in 'Durability' and 'High Functionality' respectively.

'New Automobile' is significantly inclined towards default with 82% as compared to 'Used Automobile' with 18%. In the 'New Automobile' conventional lease is almost six times more likely to default than Islamic lease whereas it is twice more likely to default in 'Used Automobile' when compared to Islamic lease. The reason of high probability of default in conventional lease could be the nature and make of lease contract. Similarly, 'Luxury' class automobiles (94%) are significantly highly likely to default than 'Economy' class (6%). In 'Luxury' class Islamic lease is considered to default only by 12% whereas conventional lease is almost seven times more likely to default.

4.1.4 BANK CONSIDERATION/ REQUIREMENTS

The most popular category of interest/mark up is 'More than 14%' which accounts for 88% in which 76% is conventional and 12% Islamic lease. Interestingly, 'Less than 6%' and '10% to 14%' are shown to least likely default whereas '6% to 10%' with likely default of 6% for both conventional and Islamic leases.

The most significant interest/mark up rate category, which is most likely to default is 'Less than 5%' with overall 76% in which 64% and 12% are conventional lease and Islamic lease respectively. Interestingly, the next important category is 'More than 11%' with 18%. The less the security deposited the greater the probability of default as is clear from 'Less than 25%' category. However, in the 'More than 50%' category the likely default is 12%, which is only conventional lease. Interestingly, in the '25% to 40%' and '40% to 50%' there is no Islamic lease whereas conventional lease is 6% in each.

5. CONCLUSIONS

After critically and empirically analysing the default risk associated with Conventional and Islamic Lease Finance, we found that Conventional Lease tend to default more as compared to Islamic Lease. The reason for this is inflexibility, hard terms, uncertain instalment amounts, and sole discretionary power of bank to change interest rate without asking the customers. Specifically, age and income tend to reduce the risk of default while price and interest rate increase the risk of being defaulted. Moreover, automobile type and unemployment show a higher risk of default. The paper not only contributes to the existing literature but helps improve the banking leasing products, reducing default risk and contribute to the bottom line of the banks.

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